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Abstract: This article talks about the management of organizational change and is a guide for students of the direction of the establishment of cultural and art institutions and management. An organization is a systematized, conscious Association of people who mobilize to achieve certain goals in terms of socio-economic production, as well as provide for the achievement of managerial tasks. One of the peculiarities of the management process itself lies in the fact that various organizational changes are carried out when socio-political processes change, positive and negative effects on the requirements of the market economy, changes in leaders and similar vital necessities arise.

Key words: organization, change, talk, task, process, positive, negative, organizational, influence, manager, direction, goal, demand, action.

УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫМИ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯМИ

Аннотация: Данная статья рассказывает об управлении организационными изменениями и является пособием для студентов направления «Создание учреждений культуры и искусства и менеджмент». Организация – это систематизированное, сознательное объединение людей, которые мобилизуются для достижения определенных целей в условиях социально-экономического производства, а также обеспечивают достижение управленческих задач. Одна из особенностей самого процесса управления заключается в том, что различные организационные изменения осуществляются при изменении общественно-политических процессов, возникновении положительных и отрицательных последствий для требований рыночной экономики, смены лидеров и тому подобных жизненных потребностей.

Ключевые слова: организация, изменение, разговор, задача, процесс, положительное, отрицательное, организационное, влияние, менеджер, направление, цель, требование, действие.

An organization is a systematized, conscious Association of people who mobilize to achieve certain goals in terms of socio-economic production, as well as

provide for the achievement of managerial tasks. One of the most important aspects of the management process itself is the transformation of socio-political processes, the positive and negative effects of market economy requirements, the change of leaders and the implementation of various organizational changes when such vital necessities arise. Let's consider to what extent organizational change management processes occur. The planned organizational changes will consist of conscious efforts by managers and employees to improve the work of the units and the organization as a whole in terms of important areas for themselves.

The objectives of such changes include:

- * increase the effectiveness of the organization's activities;
- * increase labor unity;
- * strengthening employee motivation;
- * mastering new products;
- increase market share, etc.

It should be noted that many changes should include improving the organization's ability to adapt to the external environment and changes in employee behavior. They develop many new technologies and work methods to improve the adaptation capacity of the organization, rebuild the organizational structure. Often, timeless or flexible structures are used for this, which provide the organization with the opportunity to quickly respond to new information, accelerate the transition to new operations, help odims to participate widely in decision-making, create conditions for the emergence of future leaders. A decrease in labor productivity, a decrease in the quality of work and products, a decrease in labor discipline, an inability to land employees, loss of motivation, labor disputes can be the consequences of such resistance. The most common type of resistance is when employees do not have obligations to participate in the changes taking place. Head of State Sh. From the first days of his presidential career, Mirziyoyev noted that the biggest problem for our country is the lack of personnel in accordance with the requirements of today's time, the need for specialists in all areas who master innovative and creative thinking, advanced technologies is very high.

Because during the complex transition period, the quality of education in schools declined, the name of attendance in colleges was carried. The absence of schools of creativity, the focus of cultural foci, the activities of the circle caused a number of serious problems. Our young people grow erudite, some have gone astray, and some are wandering abroad. Therefore, Shavkat Mirziyoyev looked at this issue as his own concern and pain, noting that the next day of our country depends on modern personnel, for this he put among the priorities the radical improvement of

the educational system, the upbringing of young people in the spirit of patriotism, as owners of high morale.

As the head of our state noted, it is necessary to start reforms from science in order to build confidence in the next day of Uzbekistan, to be worthy of ancestors. Because without science there will be no result in any field. In the next three years, large-scale work was carried out to effectively solve problems in this regard, to radically improve the training and management system of personnel in our country. To this end, a number of decrees and resolutions were adopted, which provided a thorough legal framework for complex efforts in this regard. Management is a vital necessity. Directing the activities of people without management towards a certain goal, it is impossible to develop all spheres of the life of society, including the sphere of culture and art. Where there is no governance, chaos, primacy, and selfishness occur. Management is a surreal process. In particular, the management of culture and the Arts has its own characteristics and some subtleties. What we want to say is that the people who control the field of culture and art – managers will have to be very aware of the spiritual and mental state, experiences, creative opportunities, as well as certain qualities of their character, which are extremely deeply contemplative, acting in the direction of literature, art, music. "Speaking about finding a way to the human soul through such a powerful force as art and culture, we all understand well that any owner of talent is a kind of universe, therefore, it is impossible to teach some reason to the people of creativity, the main thing is to try to control them. If we want to glorify Uzbekistan in the world, glorify its ancient history and bright future, keep it immortal in the memory of generations, first of all we need to educate great writers, great poets, great creators," the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan wrote in his work "high spirituality– invincible power". But one should not come to the wrong conclusion that it is impossible to lead representatives of the culture and art sphere, creators. In the above words, the people of creativity are held in high esteem and special attention is paid to the need to preserve the unique talent that is bestowed on them by God, to use their opportunity correctly, wisely in the interests of our people and our homeland. Therefore, it is necessary that the leader, working in any position in the management of the field of culture and art, be able to find the way to the hearts of the creators ' selfless work, creative potential and deep perception of the spiritual and spiritual world of our contemporaries. Management is an important and integral part of the cultural life of society. Management makes it possible to coordinate socio-economic and cultural-educational processes in society and solve large-scale tasks related to the solution and development of accumulated problems in the fields. Of particular importance in

culture and art management are such important abilities as strengthening the prestige and reputation of the manager, creating sufficient conditions for the activities of cultural and art institutions, gaining the trust of employees and creative teams, and having a positive impact on opponents in sometimes embarrassing situations.

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